

LEAN MANUFACTURING STRATEGY FOR FUTURE PRODUCTION LINES: A CASE STUDY ON VSM IMPLEMENTATION

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ABSTRACT: *The usual use of value stream mapping is studying to improve production lines that are already running. In this study, we used value stream mapping and the PDCA cycle on a production line that is still being finished and not yet operational. This work is important and unique because it uses a proactive approach to improve processes. The used method aims to create a waste-free production chain from the start. This is a big plus because it means avoiding losses with high costs and getting a very efficient production line from the start. The findings demonstrate that lean manufacturing tool (VSM) can be used on current and future production lines, and this strategy enhances production line efficiency from the outset by minimising non-value-added activities and maximising value-added activities.*

KEYWORDS: *lean manufacturing, VSM, PDCA, efficiency, waste elimination.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Many factories have shifted their focus to reducing operating costs and minimizing waste due to growing competition from low-cost countries and the economic challenges in their domestic markets. In the current competitive landscape, marked by globalization and technological progress, elevated productivity, superior quality, and minimal costs are crucial for the success of corporate enterprises (Rathi et al 2024). Companies increasingly recognize the necessity of participating in the global market and are aggressively pursuing operational strategies that bolster their competitiveness by using innovative production methods. In the last several decades, we have seen a remarkable evolution in manufacturing as we have gone from craft to mass to lean to Lean 4.0.

The Toyota Production System (TPS) is the source of Lean Production (LP) or Lean Manufacturing (LM), which Taiichi Ohno brought to Japan following the Second World War (Holweg, 2007). According to James P. Womack, Lean Manufacturing (LM) is an approach to production that aims to remove waste and reduce unneeded stages, align every step in an activity in a continuous flow, reorganize labor into cross-functional teams focused on that activity, and continuously pursue

improvement (Womak et al 1990). Lean comprises a collection of methods and tools designed to minimize waste within the production system; however, it is not a novel technology; it is extensively utilized by manufacturing companies globally (Rathiet al 2024). Besides its waste-reduction capabilities, lean manufacturing emphasizes enhancing total efficiency through optimizing processes, cost reduction, and ultimately optimizing output throughout the production line (Febianti et al 2020). Numerous innovative solutions have been developed to improve manufacturing efficiency while maintaining high standards for quality, cost, and on-time delivery. This is evident from numerous types of research that utilize lean methodologies to minimize waste as their studies focus (Mulyana et al., 2022). The implementation of LM has been extended into other sectors, such as textiles, food, construction, medical, power and electronics, ceramics, furniture, plywood, footwear, shell fabrication, and various service sectors (Alifiya; singgih, 2019) (Bakkali et al). Many studies have discussed the exploitation of lean philosophy within industrial companies (Klašnja et al., 2019). Lean manufacturing is based on pursuing simplicity, what is necessary for production, and, most importantly, customer satisfaction. Among the most famous tools and strategies of Lean Manufacturing, 5S, Kaizen,

Single-Minute Exchange of Die (SMED), Value Stream Mapping (VSM), Poka-Yok, Heijunka, kanban, are widely used in numerous industries, including manufacturing, healthcare, service industries, and others sectors (Batwara et al., 2023) (Romero; arce, 2017).

The organisation of this study is as follows. A review of the literature is given in Section II, which includes the approaches taken in earlier investigations to determine the research gap, pertinent background, and related important concepts. Section 3 delineates the framework utilised in this research, founded on the PDCA cycle and the VSM tool. Section 4 explains the application and discussion of the results, while Section 5 presents the research conclusion.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have attempted to exploit various methods, strategies, and concepts to attain excellence in applying LM in diverse businesses throughout the past 20 years (Jasti; Sharma, 2015). Lean Manufacturing is based on pursuing simplicity and, most importantly, customer satisfaction. Many tools used in Lean Manufacturing, and the foremost tool used is the Value Stream Mapping tool (VSM), addressed in this study. This study primarily focuses on the Value Stream Mapping tool (VSM) to increase an organization's overall efficiency. Identifying and minimising inventory during work and lead times is a fundamental principle of lean manufacturing, which enhances overall organisational efficiency (Rathi et al., 2021). Value Stream Mapping (VSM) is a crucial lean technique which pinpoints opportunities for implementing various lean techniques. It encompasses all process stages, including value-added and non-value-added activities, as a visual aid to uncover hidden waste and its origins. Using VSM improves the approach to Lean Production initiatives by uncovering obvious and hidden wastes affecting production throughput (Rahani; Al-ashraf, 2012). VSM is used in several fields and can be combined with many tools to achieve the desired result. According to a survey conducted by (Hodge et al., 2011) regarding applying lean principles in textile sector, nine out of eleven businesses cite VSM as their main diagnostic and representation tool. VSM can be used at all stages of lean implementation, from visual management to just-in-time (JIT). (Schwarz et al., 2011) adopted VSM as a methodology in a Hospital Centre to enhance Operating Room (OR) capacity utilization by reducing changeover and throughput time per patient. (Nallusamy et al., 2015) used environmental value stream mapping, a method that combines lean tools (VSM) and green practices, to

save waste and be environmentally friendly. To find solutions to issues and aid in creating a roadmap for the future, (Masuti; dabade, 2019) investigated VSM to identify numerous issues occurring in the production line through the use of Kaizen and lean implementation. (Kundgol et al 2021) introduced the technique of VSM in the aerospace manufacturing industry for description, analysis, and identification of potential areas of improvement within the organization's processes. Implementing VSM in a mid-sized metal factory manufacturing flanges resulted in a total annual savings of 336 hours (Narke; jayadeva, 2020). The steel and iron industries in South Africa implemented Value Stream Mapping to detect and assess industrial waste. Within a year, substantial benefits were realized, including a 28% waste minimisation and a 45% decline in waste disposal expenses. (Schoeman et al 2020). By implementing Lean Principles, Lean Thinking and using value stream mapping, a precast component manufacturing unit achieved substantial improvements where the Lead Time was reduced from 1102 to 739 minutes; daily production increased from 33 units to 40 units, and finally, the efficiency and effectiveness of the unit improved by 49% and 21.2%, respectively (Rahima shabeen et al 2022). Upon thorough analysis of the existing VSM implemented in the carton manufacturing company, recommendations were proposed to decrease the duration of each operation and enhance productivity in the domains of corrugation (5.83%), pasting (11%), punching (11.75%), and stitching (58.2%), respectively (Dinesh et al., 2022). Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) is another valuable tool implemented in this study. In (Garza-reyes et al., 2018) proposed a method based on Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) enhancement cycle to systematically execute and conduct Environmental-VSM (E-VSM) studies to supplement and support the limited body of knowledge on the application of VSM as tools to improve environmental performance and enhance the effectiveness of its application. Lean Manufacturing, Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA), Value Stream Mapping (VSM), and Problem Identification and Corrective Action (PICA) are some of the sustainability system approaches that may be used to analyze the aviation maintenance process flow and find ways to enhance it (khair et al 2024). The VSM method was synchronized with the PDCA cycle to reduce or eliminate waste constantly (Garza-reyes et al) (Chiarini, 2012). (Milosevic et al., 2021) examined the use of the PDCA cycle and Lean tools, such as Value Stream Mapping and Heijunka, to enhance the qualification of excavator frame fabrication in response to rising demand; by implementing these methodologies, the company

improved production efficiency by 10.67%. From the above recapitulation, it is clear that value stream mapping is most frequently utilized by established businesses actively producing goods and services. Our approach, however, focuses on applying this tool to a production line that had not yet entered the production phase. This allowed us to explore the potential of optimizing the production process from the beginning, ensuring that the line would be free of waste and as efficient as possible once it started operating.

3 METHODOLOGY

Value Stream Mapping is a traditional method, typically conducted with pen and paper to facilitate visualizing and comprehending the movement of information and materials as a goods progresses along the value stream (“Mike Rother et al 1999). It is a graphical tool for studying and enhancing the information and material flows inside a process or value stream. VSM aims to create a simpler, efficient, value-added process which delivers maximum customer value and eliminates waste. At the same time, PDCA stands for Plan-Do-Check-Act, used for continuous improvement, problem-solving, and organizational change management. Integrating VSM with PDCA provides a comprehensive approach to process improvement by combining the strengths of both methodologies. This section provides a detailed explanation of our PDCA and VSM approaches. Figure 1 presents the methodology used in this study.

Fig 1: Illustration of the adopted methodology.

➤ Plan phase:

During the planning phase, clear and specific goals must be reached. To develop the methodology strategy and achieve the targeted results, the following guidelines may be useful:

- **Articulate Objectives:** Precisely delineate the objectives to be accomplished. These must be specific, quantifiable, feasible, and attainable.
- **Decompose Objectives:** Divide the significant goals into smaller, achievable sub-objectives to facilitate their attainment.
- **Establish a Timeline:** Develop a timeline or schedule for each goal, including completion deadlines.
- **Allocate Resources:** Determine and assign the necessary resources (financial, human, technological) to accomplish the objectives.
- **Define Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):** Establish quantifiable metrics to monitor advancement and evaluate achievement.

➤ Do phase:

In the Do phase, the activities and tasks described in the previous phase (planning) are implemented to achieve the specified objectives. These activities are:

- **Executing the Plan:** Execute tasks and activities according to the specified schedule.
- **Defining Worker Positions within the Production Chain:** Determine the role of workers at each level of the production line. This distribution ensures fairness in distributing workloads and improving cooperation between departments while enhancing overall efficiency and reducing wasted time and resources.
- **Identification of Essential Equipment:** Determine the equipment and tools needed for each process in the production line. This ensures its implementation, improves production quality, and reduces delays resulting from insufficient equipment and tools.
- **Drawing the Value Stream Map:** A value stream map identifies the essential elements of raw materials, data and resources needed for manufacturing, making it easy to differentiate between value-added and non-value-added processes to increase efficiency and reduce waste.

➤ Check phase:

At this stage, the value stream mapping is analysed. The expected and actual results are compared to determine whether the actual performance aligns with the goals and standards set in the planning stage.

- **Check the Value Stream Map (VSM):** Analyze the map to ensure that all processes, including value-added and non-value-added processes, are functioning correctly.
- **Compare Actual Results with Goals:** compare key indicators (e.g., cycle time, wait time, throughput) against the objectives established during the planning phase to identify any differences or performance deficiencies.

➤ **Act phase:**

The "Act" phase of the PDCA cycle seeks to execute the necessary activities based on the outcomes of the "Check" phase.

- **Improve the Plan and Assure Readiness:** Modify the production schedule based on the "Check" phase's analysis to ensure that schedules and resources are appropriately matched.
- **Procedures and Guidelines Update:** Ensure all stakeholders are on board with the new process steps and make necessary revisions to operational procedures in light of discovered changes.
- **Prepare for the next PDCA cycle**

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In our research, we opt for the production process of an electrical substation system in an Algerian company as the case study. The study was carried out on a production line (Grid line) that has not yet begun manufacturing. Value Stream Mapping is typically used in an existing manufacturing line, and its analysis helps identify and eliminate waste within the process. Our study employed Value Stream Mapping for a production line that has not been established. The aim was to minimise waste from the outset and ensure a smooth and efficient initiation of operations.

➤ **Plan phase:**

During the planning phase, the desired outcomes are clearly defined and represented in Figure 2. Our study's primary goals include establishing a waste-free production line, minimising non-value-added activities, maximising value-added processes, and ensuring an efficient production system. Additionally, achieving a monthly production target of 70 cabinets while optimising available resources, such as labour and materials.

➤ **Do phase:**

The first step in the Do phase is calculating the takt time to create an optimal production line. This would determine the cycle time and the number of workers required for each task.

Fig 2: Objectives of the Plan Phase.

As part of the Do phase, we created a production line layout, which shows the distribution of workers, the location of each task, and their relative positions throughout the production line. Figure 3 shows a flow chart of a manufacturing line consisting of three workstations with 55 workers. During the implementation phase, we created a value stream map for this production chain, as shown in Figure 4. This map helped us identify and predict bottlenecks in the production process in advance if they existed so that we could take the necessary measures to eliminate them.

➤ **Check phase:**

In the check phase, we analysed the value stream map and compared the results obtained with what was planned in the planning phase, and we also compared the takt time with the cycle times presented in Figure 5. The result was that the cycle times were less than the takt time and that there was no waste in the production line, which made the production line look.

Additionally, we compared these results against the predetermined targets set during the Planning process. The results indicated that the intended goals were effectively attained, confirming the efficacy of the methods applied during production. The correlation between actual performance and planned objectives highlights the effectiveness and accuracy of our strategy in attaining operational excellence.

Since we had already determined that the production line was optimised in the previous phase, no modifications or enhancements were suggested or implemented during the ACT phase. In this step, all project stakeholders were apprised of the results obtained, including specifics on the requisite workforce and materials needed to initiate the production process.

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Fig 3: Layout of the production line.

Fig 4: The Value Stream Mapping (VSM)

Furthermore, we are preparing for a new phase and PDCA cycle to guarantee ongoing enhancement.

Fig 5: Comparison between cycle times and takt time.

5 CONCLUSION

This study highlights the adaptability and efficacy of lean manufacturing principles, demonstrating that they extend beyond traditional manufacturing organisations already operational.

Although lean manufacturing is conventionally utilised to eradicate waste, reduce costs, and improve quality in established production systems, our research indicates that these concepts can be effectively implemented in a production chain still under development. By doing so, we may establish a manufacturing line optimised from inception, devoid of waste, and aligned with the highest efficiency standards.

Including Industry 4.0 technologies in this production line will significantly enhance our continued efforts to optimise the process. Adopting intelligent technologies, automation, and data-informed decision-making will facilitate ongoing enhancements, advancing production efficiency, quality assurance, and flexibility. Through this combined approach, we aim to streamline operations and ensure that the production line can adapt and evolve in response to future challenges and opportunities, thus securing long-term success and customer satisfaction.

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